

Resistance: Transgressive and Oppositional Voice against the Oppression of Dalit Women in *Sangati*

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Abstract—This paper is about the persuasive discourse of Bama in her novel, *Sangathi*. The novel communicates the transgressive and oppositional voices of Dalit women under an oppressive social order. The text intervenes in favour of the Dalit women who suffer social, political and economical inequalities. The narrator speaks of the immense tragic situations they face and also of the insurmountable hurdles placed against their emancipation. The traditions, culture and the religions are the mind-controller that subjugate and marginalize them.

Index Terms—Resistance, Transgressive voice, Oppositional voice, Oppression, Mind-Controller and Inequalities.

I. Introduction

Bama's novel *Sangati* is profoundly peculiar and unique in many ways. The message it discourses is polysemic. It is rich and plentiful in representing different strata of society, a variety of culturally controlled mindsets and the hegemony who wielded oppressive power against the marginalized. The novel represents the transgressional and oppositional voices of women whose lived experiences reveal the structures of lives that are tragic and poignant. The novelist also expresses a political intervention against oppression by the dominant castes and even men of the oppressed communities. The novel is also an intervention against the society which is cruelly patriarchal. The interventions are in favour of deeply oppressed Dalit women and in favour of removing the inequalities suffered by them by educating Dalit girls and women.

The ideas, that being born a third girl child would fill one's courtyard with gold and that it is degrading to be born with a dark skin colour are the mind-controllers preventing the marginalized, subjugated to the other dominant ideologies. The willing acceptance of the dominant ideologies prevented them from emancipation. The discourse of the novel has a direction as it is flag posting the need for education as the only way out of their oppressions. The structure of feeling of the marginalized show that switching over to Christianity did not help much. The text says, "why on earth paraiyas alone became Christians, I don't know, but because they did so at that time; now it works out that they get no concessions from the government whatsoever" (p. 5). The girls had to do household chores because their parents went away on some errand or work. The girls also had to be baby-sitters for their younger siblings. They lived in utter poverty while their men folk were irresponsible and reclusive, drunkards,

brutal and violent. The men at home had no sensibility or love or the common pity to be of help or succor. Patti says, "We have to labour in the fields as hard as men do, and then on top of that struggle to bear and raise our children. ... Born as women what good do we get?" (p. 6) The minds of the girls did not enjoy space or silence throughout their lives. They were in terrible chains of circumstances. The text communicates the reality saying "women should never come on their own to these parts. If upper-caste fellows clap eyes on you, you're finished. They will drag you off and rape you, that's for sure" (p. 8). The narrator feels that there was no one to raise the voice of a honourable resentment to such brutality. "There was not a soul to support her or speak for her. Not even her own father. The hegemony allowed the impunity of men who say "She is my wife. I can beat her or even kill her if I want" (p. 10). There is no trace of any civilization in such a society.

The narrative also communicates the evil of competitive show of materialism among the dominant caste groups. "And when there was a similar ritual in the houses of the people who gave gifts" and support "expected an equal amount of gifts in return. Otherwise there would be complaints and fights" (p. 16). And in contrast to the people belonging to the upper strata of the hierarchy, one sees Mariamma's function had only a hutment. Her aunt cooked for her for a couple of days, gave her twenty rupees and a couple of measures of rice. The oppressive state apparatus helps only the haves. The have-nots and the Dalits can not bring to justice even if the mudalaali is guilty of crime. Savuriamma brings out the reality saying, "As far as I know, this is the first case of sexual misbehaviour that has come before the village meeting. The landowners get up to all sorts of evil in the fields. Can we bring them to justice, though? After all, we have to go crawling to them tomorrow and beg for work" (p. 25).

The feminist voice in the novel is loud, clear and positive. The real aggressors are men. The logo-phallic centred world has established a strong patriarchal society and order. On top of the pyramidal hierarchy places men as hegemony. Any resentment or transgressive acts are brutally suppressed. Fake narratives are built up in favour of men. Whether it is material ownership or the distribution of wealth or bequeathing of properties, they see to it that men are in command. Women are not even considered as beings but only as wealth, commodities and

objects of men's pleasure. The children too are considered properties or possesses of wealth when they are boys. The female child is always a property and could be traded with men in exchange of properties or as bringers of wealth. Patti says, "what do we know about justice? From your ancestor's times it has been agreed that what the men say is right. Don't you go dreaming that everything is going to change" (p. 28-29).

The dramatic feminist questions are, "why can't we be the same as boys? we aren't allowed to talk loudly or laugh noisily; even while we sleep we can't stretch out on our backs nor lie face down on our bellies. We always have to walk with our heads bowed down" (p. 29). She could perceive that these restrictions were to keep the female under men's control. Even if the girl is screaming in hunger, she cannot eat first. She is allowed to have her meals only after men had finished and gone. She perceives that existentialism says that the soul of human beings has no gender. Patti says that these men centred morality and norms are already established in many texts.

The situation did not change even in the Churches. "If it was like this at home, it was even worse at Church" (p. 32). The choice of the Church to enact the scene of nativity were men dressed up as the virgin Mary. "But they won't let a women do even that much" (p. 33). A few pages after this, the narrative tells, "There were many amongst us who could sing really beautiful. But never to this day has a single one of us been allowed to sing in public" (p. 35). The transgressive voice speaks out the structure of feeling to express the tragic conditions of their lived experience. "The position of women is both pitiful and humiliating really. In the fields they have to escape from upper-caste men's molestations. At Church they must lick the priest's shoes and be his slaves while he threatens them with tales of God, Heaven and Hell. ... before they have had a chance to cook some kanji or lie down and rest, they have to submit themselves to their husband's torment" (p. 35).

The tragic conclusion of the narrator's mother is: "It's not so easy to get away, once you are married. Once you've put your head in the mortar, can you escape from the pestle?" (p. 44). The textual intervention shows the seeds of resistance to the dominant social order. The text says, "... a variety of emotions grew in my heart: anger, excitement, fury, pride, resentment, hatred" (p. 44).

The narrative critically analyses the reason behind the violent behaviour of Dalit men at home. It states, "... all that violence was because there was nowhere else for them to exert their male pride or to show off their authority. All that suppressed anger was vented when they came home and beat up their wives to a pulp" (p. 65). They could not fight back or argue their rights with the landlords but the Dalit women were tormented both at home and at large. They were the worst sufferers because the upper caste women also treated them with contempt. The upper caste were not in freedom either but treated the Dalit women as creatures of a different species. The narrator has the right perception to see that the Dalit women freely moved

about, earned their own money. They enjoyed much space and freedom than the upper-caste women. The pity is that the Dalit women did not receive their own men's support. "... everyone, starting from the police, choose to blame and humiliate the women of our community" (p. 66).

The women characters are quite heroic in their sphere of life because of their ardent pursuit to earn wages by rightful means, and to take care of the children and to have minimal food, shelter and clothes. They show intelligent economic sense. They could save some money too. If they could only be financially supported, they could show the world that it is possible to narrow economic inequalities. The Dalit women, unlike their husbands are not prodigal spenders and neither are they seekers of costly pleasures. "Our women have an abundant will to survive however hard they might have to struggle for their last breath. Knowingly or unknowingly, we find ways of coping in the best way we can" (p. 68).

The narrative raises certain existentialist questions regarding the purpose of human life. The general problems of division, discrimination, disorder and the resulting pain, horror and the uncertainty everywhere cannot be solved by traditions, religion or even by political maneuvering. The discourse in the novel perceives the immediacy of a life which is independent and individualistic. Religions and politics thrive by promising and punishing. They control the consciousness of the general polity and have failed to solve humanity's existential, spiritual or social problems. The writer says, "It's by calling on all this stuff about God, the promises, ... and Heaven and everlasting Hell that the priests and nuns frighten the life out of us. But God created us so that we can be happy and free. ... God does not want us to be living like slaves to the day we die" (p. 95). The meaning and message of the novel is clear. It signifies that men are peys and the women the suffering angels. The peys have defeated the angels and have enslaved them. If heaven like situation is to be created this devils ruling over angels must be reversed. The text says, "However much we strain to leap forward, caste holds us down like a tap root. It is at the centre of religion, politics, education, and every other wretched thing" (p. 102).

She did not want to hide her identity to solve this setback. She asks, "Why should I tell a lie and live a false life?" (p. 121). Hers is a fine sensibility and represents a fine culture. Women of other castes do not face this problem. Only Dalit women are denied the basic right to pay and rent a house. The question which she raises is apt. "Why shouldn't a woman belong to no one at all but herself" (p. 121). The text leaves off with the positive hope with boys and girls brought up in equal freedom and later as men and women who live as one with equal rights. "The injustice, violence and inequalities will come to and end" (p. 123).

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